

Effects of linear landscape elements on ecosystem services supply and trade-offs in contrasting agricultural landscapes

Abstract

Linear landscape elements, such as field margins, are agricultural practices whose adoption is supported by agri-environmental climate measures (AECMs). AECMs are meant to improve ecological conditions on farms and surrounding areas. The effectiveness of AECMs to enhance the supply of multiple ESs is still debated and knowledge on trade-offs and synergies among ESs under different practices stemming from AECMs is still lacking. We aimed at assessing the potential of AECMs that promote the implementation of linear landscape elements to provide high levels of multiple ESs and at analyzing possible trade-offs at landscape level in different geographical contexts. We assessed the potential effects of linear landscape elements (woody, grassy, flower and a mix) on six ESs (food provision, pollination, pest control, climate sequestration, aesthetics and habitat maintenance), combining scenarios and spatially explicit modelling approaches. Our results showed the positive effects of linear landscape elements on all regulating and cultural ESs. The more abundant the linear elements, the higher the overall ESs supply. However, the effect of linear landscape elements on multiple ESs depended on the types of linear elements and the geographical context of their implementation. Our analyses give insights on the efficiency of AECMs on multiple environmental targets. Our approach is a first step towards a general framework for an ex-ante integrated analysis of AECMs that can be used to design policies. From a more practical perspective, our results can form a basis for additional payments for AECMs. Our study also confirms the relevance of the EU biodiversity strategy that commits to ensure at least 10% of agricultural area as high-biodiversity landscape features such as linear landscape elements.

Keywords

Agri-environmental schemes; field margins; buffer strips; agricultural practices, modelling; scenarios

Highlights

- Modelling changes in ES supply under several agricultural practices promoted by agri-environmental measures
- Linear elements in agroecosystems support high supply of regulating and cultural ES
- Higher amount of linear elements leads to higher level of regulating and cultural ES supply
- The effects of the linear elements depend on their type (flower, tree, grass and mix) and on the targeted ES
- Effectiveness of linear elements depends on the conditions of the landscape in which they are implemented

38 1. Introduction

39 Several policy instruments have been introduced in Europe to incentivize farmers to manage their land
40 more sustainable (Villanueva *et al.*, 2015). For example, agri-environmental climate measures (AECMs)
41 contracts are an important instrument of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). AECMs are meant to
42 contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, and to improve ecological conditions on farms
43 and surrounding areas for halting and reversing biodiversity loss, enhancing ecosystem services (ESs)
44 and preserve habitats and landscapes (*Official Journal of the European Union, 2021*¹). In the case of
45 AECM contracts farmers commit themselves on a voluntary basis to adopt environmentally-friendly
46 farming practices or measures that go beyond the cross-compliance level (i.e. the set standards and
47 requirements for receiving direct EU income support). In return, farmers receive payments that provide
48 compensation for additional costs for implementing these measures. Farmers get also compensate for
49 possible lost income due to lower yields because of applying those environmentally friendly farming
50 measures, for example lower or no use of agrochemicals, specific modes of crop rotation, organic
51 farming and the protection of landscapes or species by conserving their habitats (Uthes and Matzdorf,
52 2013).

53 Several agri-environmental measures exist, such as the construction and maintenance of nature-friendly
54 (river) banks, delayed mowing, conservation grazing, the introduction or restoration of linear elements or
55 buffer strips along agricultural fields, and making use of specific crop rotations. Each measure has
56 specific requirements that the land manager must meet. For example, in linear elements/buffer strips
57 next to a field, a certain percentage of the surface must be covered with flowers or grass species during
58 a certain period.

59 The effectiveness of these policy instruments to enhance ESs is however still debated. On the one hand,
60 studies assessing the effectiveness of environmental friendly measures have generally determined
61 positive effects on various aspects and indicators of biodiversity (Dietschi *et al.*, 2007; Aviron *et al.*,
62 2009; Kampmann *et al.*, 2012). Other ecological benefits of these measures have been demonstrated as
63 well, for example on water quality regulation and erosion prevention (Galler *et al.*, 2015). On the other
64 hand, several studies have found that AECM contracts were not sufficient for generating environmental
65 benefits (Kleijn *et al.*, 2001; Kleijn *et al.*, 2004; Pe'er *et al.*, 2014) and the environmental benefits that
66 were demonstrated were highly context-dependent (Wallander and Hand, 2011; Uthes and Matzdorf,
67 2013; Moxey and White, 2014).

68 Despite a growing literature on the possible environmental benefits of environmental friendly measures,
69 we identified four main knowledge gaps. First, AECM contracts often target one specific ES. Yet,
70 measures implemented to improve the supply of one specific ES might have added value for other ESs
71 (i.e., synergies) while the supply of other ESs might decrease (i.e., trade-offs). Olivieri *et al.* (2021)
72 underlined the difficulty of designing and implementing one single type of AECM contract that enhances
73 all ESs produced by agriculture, independently of the geographical context. More knowledge about
74 synergies and trade-offs between ESs within different landscapes is required to assist land use planners
75 in effectively implementing AECM contracts. Second, little is still known, to our knowledge, about the
76 variability of the effect of agri-environmental measures across geographical contexts. As ESs supply is
77 highly site- and management-specific in agricultural landscapes (Le Clec'h *et al.*, 2019), a better
78 understanding of effects of geographical contexts is critical to assess the reproducibility of case studies
79 and the universality of the effects of measures. In addition, while a specific spatial targeting of measures
80 could increase the effectiveness of the measures (Frueh-Mueller *et al.*, 2018), it is unknown how ESs
81 synergies and trade-offs are influenced by spatial targeting and by the total amount of land under AECMs
82 contracts. Finally, only very few scientific studies conduct ex-ante analyses of the impacts of
83 environmental friendly measures on multiple environmental targets. However, such knowledge would
84 also help to discuss implications of policy targets (Verburg *et al.*, 2016).

¹ Official Journal of the European Union L 435/1 - Regulation 2021/2015 article 6 d and f, p28

85 While several studies focus on the policy performance of AECMs contracts, for example through the total
86 uptake of the AECM contracts measured in the amount of area covered or number of farmers
87 participating, the literature on modeling and analyzing impacts of measures on multiple ESs is still
88 limited. This paper aims at assessing the potential of agri-environmental measures to provide high levels
89 of multiple ES in three landscapes and to analyze possible trade-offs at landscape level in different
90 geographical contexts. More specifically, we are answering the following questions that cover the four
91 abovementioned research gaps: 1) How does the type and proportion of linear elements affect synergies
92 and trade-offs between ESs? And 2) How do the effects of linear elements differ across contrasting
93 landscapes?

94 We restricted our analyses to linear landscape elements on field margins. More specifically, we focused
95 on the effects of 1) flower strips, 2) un-mowed grass strips, 3) hedgerows at the edges of the
96 agricultural fields and 4) an equal mixture of flower and un-mowed grass and trees. Several studies have
97 demonstrated the effects of linear landscape elements on pollination (Krimmer *et al.*, 2019; Geppert *et al.*
98 *et al.*, 2020), biodiversity (Van Vooren *et al.*, 2017), pest control (Tschumi *et al.*, 2016), carbon
99 sequestration (Van Vooren *et al.*, 2017), energy production (Smith *et al.*, 2021) and aesthetics (Bullock
100 *et al.*, 2021), in various agricultural landscapes across Europe. While linear elements can be
101 implemented in combination with other management measures (e.g., extensification), we did not
102 consider such combinations.

103 Our analyses shed light on ES synergies and trade-offs in agricultural landscapes and give insights on the
104 environmental efficiency of AECM contracts which include linear elements. Our approach is a first step
105 towards a general framework for an ex ante integrated analysis of AECM contracts. Our study regions
106 build a promising basis to scale up our assessment to other agricultural landscapes facing the wide-
107 spread trade-off between agricultural intensification and ESs supply. From a more practical perspective,
108 our results could help optimizing the supply of multiple ESs in different agricultural landscapes and thus
109 be a basis for additional payments for environmental friendly measures, for example in the form of
110 carbon credits.

111 2. Material and Methods

112 2.1. Study areas

113 Mixed small scale agricultural (mosaic) landscapes play a crucial role in global food security and
114 contribute to human well-being through the supply of food and fodder and a wide range of ESs (Rusch *et al.*
115 *et al.*, 2013; Kirchwegger *et al.*, 2020). In agricultural areas, trade-offs occur between provisioning and
116 regulating services (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005), although the relationship between ESs in
117 agricultural landscapes is complex (Power, 2010).

118 This paper relies on three study regions across Europe: Achterhoek (the Netherlands), Bornholm
119 (Denmark) and Órség National Park (Hungary). The three study areas are characterized by their
120 landscapes of small scale mixed agriculture and the presence of Natura2000 areas (Fig. 1).

121 The Achterhoek is an agriculturally dominated region, located in the province of Gelderland, in the
122 eastern part of the Netherlands. It spans over 1,476 km². Its topography is relatively flat, with an
123 elevation of around 28 m. The average annual precipitation is 827 mm and the average annual
124 temperature is around 10.6 °C. The landscape is dominated by agriculture taking up 54% of the area
125 and built-up area and infrastructure covering 21% of the area. Forests cover 13% of the area, dry nature
126 types cover 5% of the area and wet nature types cover 1% of the area. Urban green covers 3% of the
127 area and water covers 2% of the area. In the eastern part of the region some small areas are allocated
128 as Natura2000 sites (among others with raised bog). The agricultural landscape is characterized by
129 hedgerows (bocage) and small agricultural parcels. The main land use in the region is grassland (38% of
130 the total area). The main crops are maize (20% of agricultural area) and potato (3% of agricultural
131 area). The average field size in the Achterhoek is 2.1 hectares. Approximately 405,000 people live in the

132 Achterhoek (CBS²). The region is known for its aesthetics and scenery, which is confirmed by the more
133 than 3 million nights spent at tourist accommodations (Eurostat³). Since 2016 the Dutch farmers can
134 only jointly apply for CAP-AECMs, organized with help of agri-environmental collectives. The certified
135 collectives are the link between the individual farmers who implement the environmental friendly
136 measures and the government that provides the subsidies (see for more details: Boonstra *et al.* (2021).
137 The Netherlands is divided in 40 collectives. In the Achterhoek one collective is active, the Vereniging
138 Agrarisch Landschap Achterhoek (VALA; <https://de-vala.nl/>) with approximately 900 members. The
139 vision of VALA is to increase biodiversity through conservation and development of the Achterhoek
140 cultural landscape. The collective prepares management plans together with the farmers, aiming for
141 spatial coordination of measures and also provides management guidance to the farmers (see also
142 (Bredemeier *et al.*, 2022).

143

² Bevolkingsontwikkeling; regio per maand (cbs.nl)

³ Statistics | Eurostat (europa.eu)

a)

b)

c)

d)

- Annual crops
- Perennial crops
- Grasslands
- Forest
- Nature, dry
- Nature, wet
- Water
- Built-up and infrastructure

145 Fig. 1. Location (a) and current land-use of the three study areas: (b) Achterhoek (the Netherlands), (c)
146 Bornholm (Denmark) and (d) Órség National Park (Hungary).

147 Bornholm is a Danish Island in the Baltic Sea. It spans over 588 km² inhabited by 40 thousand people.
148 Its topography is undulating, with an elevation ranging between 0 and 163 m. The average annual
149 precipitation is 705 mm and the average annual temperature is 9.2 °C. The landscape is dominated by
150 agriculture taking up 60% of the area and forest covering 17% of the area. Built-up area and
151 infrastructure cover 13% of the area, dry nature types 5% and wet nature types 1% of the area. The
152 island has several areas allocated as Natura2000 sites, with the largest covering 61 km². Pig farming is
153 the most important farm type managing 37% of the agricultural area, arable farms cover 17% of the
154 agricultural area and cattle farms, mainly dairy, manage 17% of the agricultural area. The average farm
155 size is 92 ha with the largest 13% of the farms managing 52% of the agricultural area while the smallest
156 47% of the farmers manage 5% of the agricultural area. The main crops are wheat (35% of the
157 agricultural area), barley, (25%) and seed production and grass in rotation (both covering 8% of the
158 agricultural area). The average field size on Bornholm is 4.9 hectares. In terms of AECMs, organic
159 farming is the most important involving 5% of the agricultural area. Agreements on conservation grazing
160 covers almost 600 ha, corresponding to 43% of the permanent grassland. AECMs targeting the
161 establishment of hedgerows are currently not available in Denmark, but will be included in an eco-
162 scheme from 2023.

163 Órség National Park is both a nationally protected area and a Natura2000 site, situated in the West of
164 Hungary, close to the borders of Slovenia and Austria. It covers 440 km² with a hilly topography, ranging
165 between 200–390 m. The average annual precipitation is 700–800 mm and the average annual
166 temperature is around 9.5 °C. The landscape has kept its natural character due to its location within the
167 Iron Curtain buffer zone. It is characterized by a mosaic of land covers, dominated by forests (65%) and
168 followed by grasslands (11%) in the valleys and arable fields (20%) on the higher elevations. Órség is
169 sparsely populated with only 18 thousand inhabitants. Forty four settlements, most of them with a
170 population below 500 people, are partly or entirely within the national park. Settlements are typically
171 surrounded by extensive orchards, nursery gardens and vegetable gardens. Farming practices are
172 typically traditional and extensive, due to poor soil quality, irregular topography and scattered ownership
173 structure. The average field size in Órség is 2.4 hectares. Being a Natura2000 site, obligatory measures
174 already exist for grassland, such as prohibition of ploughing or overseeding, elimination of invasive
175 plants, use of nature-friendly mowing and leaving uncut refuge grass areas on 5-10% of the field.
176 Voluntary agri-environmental schemes are also available since 2002, but only 3% of the agricultural area
177 has been enrolled in one of the three schemes High Nature Value (HNV) grassland for birds, HNV
178 grasslands for butterflies or HNV arable fields over the last 10 years. In the first two schemes, measures
179 include the unmown grass-strips, in the last one field margins without any use of chemicals. Since the
180 establishment of Órség National Park in 2002, tourism has become a major activity.

181 2.2. Targeted ecosystem services and agri-environmental measures

182 While a range of ESs are provided by small scale agricultural landscapes (Kirchweger *et al.*, 2020), we
183 focused on quantifying six indicators of ESs, as classified in the CICES (Common International
184 Classification of Ecosystem Services; (Haines-Young, 2018)). We analyzed potential effects of linear
185 landscape elements on food provision, pollination, pest control, habitat maintenance, climate regulation
186 and aesthetics (Table 1). These six indicators were chosen for three main reasons. First, previous studies
187 had shown that the ESs characterized by these indicators are likely to respond land-use land-cover
188 change, in an agricultural landscape (Krimmer *et al.*, 2019; Van Vooren *et al.*, 2017; Tschumi *et al.*,
189 2016; Bullock *et al.*, 2021). This point makes them interested in analyzing the potential response of
190 alternative agricultural practices of agricultural socio-ecological systems. Secondly, these ESs were
191 provided from different biophysical processes, making them complementary to each other. Finally, the
192 indicators had been used in previous studies to characterize the ESs considered in our analyses.

193 Table 1. Indicators used per ES

ES category	ES	Indicators*
Regulation and maintenance	Pollination	Pollination potential of crops (%)
	Natural pest control	Relative density of natural enemies in agricultural crops (%)
	Global climate regulation	Sequestered carbon in the vegetation (tC/ha)
	Habitat maintenance	Index built from: Proportion (%) of cropland and orchards, pastures, (semi-)natural ecosystems and artificial surfaces; Shannon's Diversity Index (-); the Euclidean Nearest-Neighbor Distance (m)
Cultural	Aesthetics	Index built from: Shannon's Diversity Index (-); Patch Density (per km ²) mean Shape Index (-)
Provisioning	Food provision	The total added market price of main crops per ha (Euro)

194 *For habitat maintenance and aesthetics we have used the sum of normalized results of the three mentioned indicators for our
195 analyses.

196 2.3. Modelling and statistical approaches:

197 We developed a tree-step spatially explicit modelling approach. First, we used spatially explicit
198 environmental data for agricultural fields in three European study regions to calculate supply ESs.
199 Second, we calculated the change in the ESs supply, under different scenarios, i.e., when challenging the
200 type and proportion of linear elements across the landscapes. Third, we analyzed trade-offs, synergies,
201 and bundles for each of the scenarios.

202 2.3.1. Spatially-explicit calculation of ecosystem services

203 *Pollination and natural pest control*

204 We used the spatially-explicit Natural Capital Model (NC-Model) to estimate effects of linear landscape
205 elements on the supply of the two ESs: pollination and natural pest control. The NC-Models built on
206 process-based approaches to map ESs. To do so, the NC-Models required inputs on land use and habitat
207 quality for pollinators and natural enemies and use spatial explicit models to combine the input data (i.e.,
208 spatial data and reference values for habitat quality) with spatial distribution of pollinators and natural
209 enemies to predict the potential pollination (%) or relative abundance of natural enemies (%) in crop
210 fields. For information about the NC-Model, see de Knegt *et al.* (2022). Appendix 1 shows the maps of
211 the spatial distribution of pollination and pest control services for the baseline scenario and for the
212 situation where 12.5% of the whole utilized agricultural area was covered by hedgerows.

213 The pollination service was primarily provided by the ecosystems in the landscape surrounding the crop
214 fields (de Knegt *et al.*, 2022). In the crop pollination model the potential pollination by wild pollinators
215 was calculated based on the availability of resources in the agricultural landscape and their dispersal
216 abilities. The pollinators required suitable nesting habitats as well as sufficient floral resources.
217 Parameterization of habitat suitability was based on a meta-study for temperate regions (Kennedy *et al.*,
218 2013), therefore the same parameterization was used for all study areas in our study. The indicator used
219 for the pollination service was potential pollination (%), which relates to the percentage of the production
220 of the crop that depends on insect pollination could be provided by the surrounding landscape. This
221 indicator could be combined with crop specific values for potential production loss in the absence of
222 pollinators, to get a measure for avoided production loss in ton/ha or euro/ha. Crop specific values for
223 potential production loss in the absence of pollinators was however not available for all study sites,
224 therefore potential pollination is used as indicator.

225 Natural pest control also depends on (semi-)natural ecosystems in the landscape surrounding the crop
226 fields. In the NC-model the relative densities of three natural enemy groups (crawling predators, flying
227 predators and flying predators that require nectar) in crop fields were calculated based on possible
228 source habitats (e.g. overwinter habitats) in the surrounding landscape combined with the dispersal
229 abilities of the natural enemies (de Knegt *et al.*, 2022). One of these predator groups also required floral
230 resources to provide the service. Parameterization of the habitat quality per land use type was based on
231 expert judgement based on international scientific literature, therefore the same parameterization was
232 used for all three study sites in our study. The indicator used for this service was relative predator
233 density (%) of the three natural enemy groups combined, this was the density relative to the set density
234 of 100% of the most suitable source habitat (e.g. forest edges). The relative density was not linked to
235 the actual contribution of natural enemies to pest control in the field, but it indicated the potential for
236 natural pest control.

237 *Global climate regulation*

238 For global climate regulation we used the approach used for Natural Capital Accounting in the
239 Netherlands (Statistics Netherlands and WUR, 2021). This model required input of land use data and
240 combined this input with carbon sequestration rates in above and below ground biomass per land use
241 category. The model was used to quantify the change in total carbon sequestered per year in the linear
242 landscape elements. Sequestration rates of soil carbon were not accounted for. Parameterization for the
243 Netherlands was also used for the study sites in Denmark and Hungary.

244 *Aesthetics and habitat maintenance*

245 Following Van Bussel *et al.* (2020), we computed several landscape metrics to capture landscape
246 aesthetics and habitat maintenance. We used ArcGIS® software and Patch Analyst v5.1.0.7 software
247 (Rempel *et al.*, 2012) Patch Analyst Download - Extension to the ArcGIS® software system
248 (informer.com) to calculate all landscape metrics, based on the land cover maps. The land cover maps
249 were resampled into a 10 x 10m spatial resolution in order to calculate the landscape metrics because of
250 computation times. To quantify the two ESs, no differences were made between the four different types
251 of strips.

252 We estimated aesthetics based on three landscape metrics, as proposed by Frank *et al.* (2013): the
253 Shannon's Diversity Index, the Patch Density and the Mean Shape Index. These three metrics capture
254 the landscape diversity and the complexity of the shapes of the patches in the landscape. The metrics
255 were computed from the land use land cover maps that we first clustered, based on the diversity of the
256 land cover classes (Frank *et al.*, 2013). An aesthetics index was calculated from the three individual
257 metrics after we normalised them. To do so, we identified the maximal variation of each individual
258 metrics across all scenarios, including the baseline situation, per country. We then divided the value of
259 the three metrics by the maximal value identified in the previous step. We summed up the three
260 normalized metrics to get the aesthetics index, per country.

261 We estimated habitat maintenance based on three landscape metrics. The composition of the landscape
262 was captured through the proportion (%) of (semi-)natural ecosystems, as opposed to cropland and
263 orchards, pastures, and artificial surfaces. The configuration of the landscape was captured through the
264 richness of land-cover types in the landscape (Shannon's Diversity Index) and landscape connectivity
265 (inverse Euclidean Nearest-Neighbour Distance at class level for the (semi-)natural ecosystems
266 connectivity). See (McGarigal and Marks, 1995) for detailed explanations of the landscape metrics. We
267 calculated a biodiversity index, by computing the sum of the three individual metrics, following the
268 procedure described above to compute the aesthetics index.

269

270 *Food provision*

271 We estimated food provision using a lookup table that linked the main crops in each study area with their
272 average productivity (yield per hectare in ton/ha) and price (Euro per ton). Information about the
273 average productivity and prices were derived from national statistics, in the case of Hungary and the
274 Netherlands, and information from farms in Bornholm. To evaluate the effects of linear landscape
275 elements on food supply, we first multiplied the total cultivated land by the average productivity, to get
276 the total production per crop and per scenario. In order to aggregate the information for all crops, we
277 subsequently multiplied the total production of each crop by the price per crop and added up these
278 numbers.

279 2.3.2. Scenarios of linear elements allocation

280 We performed a scenario analysis to analyze the effect of the type and proportion of linear elements on
281 the supply of ESs (Fig. 2). The current land cover maps for the three study areas were used as the
282 baseline scenario. For the Danish and Hungarian study areas, no existing linear elements were displayed
283 on the current land cover maps, probably due to the resolution of the available maps. For the Dutch
284 study area existing linear elements were displayed on the map and these elements were made part of
285 the Dutch baseline scenario. For each of the study areas, we then added randomly 10 m wide linear
286 elements to the current land cover maps until a coverage of 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, 10% and 12.5% of the
287 whole utilized agricultural area was achieved (see Figure 2 how this look likes for a random cutout of the
288 Dutch case). For each coverage four maps were created, with 100% hedgerows (i.e. woody strips),
289 100% grassy strips, 100% flower strips and a balanced mix of woody (33%), grassy (33%) and flower
290 (33%) strips.

291 We arbitrary decided to allocate linear elements to the eastern border of the agricultural fields displayed
292 on the current land cover maps. If a field was already bordered by a linear element (in the Dutch case),
293 no additional element was added to this field. If the total area covered by elements was lower than our
294 targeted coverage, we then also added elements to the southern or northern border of the fields. In the
295 latter case, one field can thus be bordered by several elements.

296

297 Fig. 2. Schematic illustration for a cutout of the Achterhoek of the random allocation of the linear
 298 elements with in blue a) 2.5%, b) 5.0%, c) 7.5%, d) 10.0%, and e) 12.5% of the whole utilized
 299 agricultural area covered by linear elements with a width of 10 m. The purple areas indicate parcels with
 300 existing agri-environmental measures. Different shades of brown indicate different land covers.

301 The location of the linear elements affects the level of supply of ESs and biodiversity (Moonen and
 302 Marshall, 2001). However, farmers' decisions about where and which linear elements to implement on
 303 their fields encompass more factors than just the effect on the supply of ESs (Wang *et al.*, 2021), that
 304 might mainly be dependent on practical considerations, such as soil quality, accessibility. Including this
 305 complex decision-making process is beyond the scope of our research, so we opted for a random
 306 assignment of the position of the linear elements, following Huber *et al.* (2022). We repeated this
 307 random distribution of the linear landscape elements five times. By applying five iterations, we accounted
 308 for uncertainties related to the decision making-process by farmers. For each iteration, we estimated the
 309 supply of all individual ESs. We then calculated the average supply for each individual ES, across the five
 310 iterations for one given share of linear landscape elements (ranging from 2.5 to 12.5% covering the
 311 utilized agricultural area). Except for the agricultural land replaced by the linear elements, we assumed
 312 that the use of the remaining land did not change. By following this methodology, our results represent
 313 the range of potential effects rather than a prediction of actual land-use.

314 To calculate the change (i.e. additional or reduced supply of ESs) we used this formula:

$$315 \text{ Change} = \frac{ES_{LS} - ES_{BL}}{ES_{BL}} \times 100\% \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

316 With ES_{LS} being the estimated ES provision under one of the linear element scenario and ES_{BL} the
 317 estimated ES provision under the baseline situation.

318

319 2.3.3. Bundles and trade-offs analyses

320 In the final step, we analyzed bundles, trade-offs and synergies between ES at the landscape level, in
321 the baseline situation and in the scenario with 12.5% coverage of linear elements. We relied on the
322 modelled supply of the six ESs indicators, in each of the three study regions. First, we calculated the
323 average supply of the six individual ESs indicators for each type of linear landscape elements and
324 scenario (baseline situation and 12.5% coverage of linear elements), across the five simulations. Second,
325 we standardized the average supplies. To standardize these averages, we identified the maximal
326 variation of each ES indicator among the following scenarios: the baseline situation and the four
327 scenarios with the highest share of landscape elements (12.5%). We used these maximal variations to
328 get a normalized value for each ES, by dividing the value of the six ESs by the maximal value identified
329 in the previous step. Normalised values were comprised between 0 and 100. Finally, we calculated the
330 standard deviation of the six ESs indicators for each type of linear landscape elements and scenario,
331 across the five simulations. Standard deviation gives information about the variability of ESs supply over
332 the five simulations. All data analyses were conducted in R (Team., 2022).

333 2.4. Input data for the simulations

334 The supply of ESs in agricultural landscapes depends on both management and environmental drivers
335 (Le Clec'h *et al.*, 2019). We combine data on land use, including the location of the fields and type of
336 agricultural production, land cover, soil type and various environmental features related to the land-use
337 land cover. Sources of the data is given in table 2 for the three study areas.

338

Data	Inputs in ES models	Source		
		Denmark	Hungary	The Netherlands
Land cover	Pollination, Pest control, Climate regulation, Aesthetics, Habitat maintenance	Basemap Denmark (https://envs.au.dk/en/research-areas/society-environment-and-resources/land-use-and-gis/basemap)	Habitat map of Órség National Park, internal data	Ecosystem type map of the Netherlands, 2020 (update of https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/maatschappij/natuur-en-milieu/natuurlijk-kapitaal/themas/ecosysteemtypen)
Forest type	Climate regulation	University of Copenhagen, internal data.	Habitat map of Órség National Park	Ecosystem type map of the Netherlands, 2020
Field location	All	The Agricultural Agency (https://lbst.dk/landbrug/genetiske-ressourcer/kort-og-markblokke/)	Map of agricultural parcels, internal data	Netherlands Enterprise Agency (https://www.pdok.nl/download/-/article/basisregistratie-gewaspercelen-brp-)
Crop type	Food production, pollination, pest control	The Agricultural Agency (https://lbst.dk/landbrug/genetiske-ressourcer/kort-og-markblokke/)	Crop type map of Órség National Park, internal data	Netherlands Enterprise Agency (https://www.pdok.nl/download/-/article/basisregistratie-gewaspercelen-brp-)
Crop yield	Food production	Statistikbanken (https://www.statistikbanken.dk/statbank5a/default.asp?w=1920)	Hungarian Central Statistical Office (https://www.ksh.hu/stadat?lang=hu&theme=ara)	Statistics Netherlands and WUR, crop production map 2020 (https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/publicatie/2021/22/natuurlijk-kapitaalrekeningen-nederland-2013-2018)
Crop price	Food production	Statistikbanken (https://www.statistikbanken.dk/statbank5a/default.asp?w=1920)	Hungarian Central Statistical Office (https://www.ksh.hu/stadat?lang=hu&theme=ara)	Wageningen Economic Research (Wisman, A., 2020. NSO-typering agrarische bedrijven 2020; Normen en uitgangspunten bij typering agrarische bedrijven in Nederland. Wageningen, Wageningen Economic Research, Nota 2021-012; https://edepot.wur.nl/537610)

341 3. Results

342 3.1. Effects of type and proportion of linear elements ES at the landscape level

343 Across the three study areas the increase of linear elements led to an increase in the provision of all six
344 ESs, except for the food provision. The variability across the five iterations per scenario was very low for
345 all six ESs and all three study areas, showing that the location of the linear elements does not affect the
346 change in the ESs.

347 3.1.1. Pollination

348 Figure 3a shows that under the baseline situation the mean potential pollination by wild pollinators is
349 almost at saturation in Órség National park (98%) and reaching potential in the Achterhoek (95%). In
350 contrast, the current landscape of Bornholm provided a lower potential pollination of 62%. The difference
351 in potential pollination could be explained by the current land use in the three study areas. In Órség
352 national park, large parts of the area were covered by forest (Fig. 1), which was characterized by a
353 rather high habitat suitability for wild pollinators. In the Achterhoek, large areas were covered by
354 grasslands (Fig. 1) which provided also habitats albeit with a relatively low quality. In Bornholm the
355 landscape was dominated by fields with arable crops, which were considered not suitable as habitat for
356 wild pollinators.

357 Fig. 3b-d shows that a higher coverage of agricultural land by linear landscape elements resulted in a
358 higher supply of the ES pollination. Importantly, we observed diminishing returns as the relative benefits
359 of linear landscape elements were lower in areas that already had high habitat suitability under the
360 baseline situation. Largest increases were simulated for Bornholm, smallest for Órség national park.
361 Comparing the coverages showed that the delivery of potential pollinators in the Achterhoek increased
362 relatively the most from the baseline to the 2.5% scenario. An increase from 10.0% to 12.5% gave
363 relatively the least additional potential pollination. In Bornholm the relative increase in pollination
364 potential with a 2.5% additional coverage was almost linear: every 2.5% extra coverage gave
365 approximately a comparable extra pollination potential, although the increase was lesser when the
366 coverage of linear elements went from 7.5 to 10%, compared to the other changes in the amount of
367 linear elements. Additional coverage in Órség national park with linear landscape elements gave only
368 little additional potential pollination, however the change from 10.0% to 12.5% led to the highest
369 relative change in potential pollination. The different types of linear landscape elements showed similar
370 trends across coverages: a higher coverage implied higher ES supply, for any types of linear elements.
371 Implementing hedgerows was, however, most beneficial to supply additional pollination. In all three case
372 study areas a coverage of 2.5% with hedgerows provided approximately the same additional potential
373 supply as a coverage of 5.0% with grassy strips.

374

375 Fig. 3 (a) total pollination potential (%) for the three study areas under the baseline scenario; and the
 376 difference in supply in comparison with the baseline scenario for (b) the Achterhoek, (c) Bornholm, and
 377 (d) Órség National Park for the different coverages and different type of linear landscape elements (%).
 378 Please note the different scales of the y-axis. The graph shows the average ES provision across the five
 379 iterations, for each scenario and study area.

380 3.1.2. Natural pest control

381 The differences between the study areas in the supply of natural pest control (Fig. 4a) were much
 382 smaller than for the potential pollination supply (Fig. 3a). Under the baseline scenario the relative
 383 predator density was the highest in the Achterhoek (15%) and the lowest in Bornholm (10%). Adding
 384 linear landscape elements considerably enhanced the supply of natural pest control. In the Achterhoek,
 385 10% extra coverage of the agricultural landscape with flower strips or hedgerows more than doubled the
 386 relative predator density. In Bornholm, 5% extra coverage of the agricultural landscape with flower
 387 strips, hedgerows or a mixture approximately doubled the relative density. The additional supply of
 388 natural pest control was smaller in Órség national park: 12.5% additional coverage with flower strips or
 389 hedgerows gives approximately 90% additional relative predator density. The smaller added value in
 390 Órség national park could be explained by the large variation in agricultural fields sizes in Órség national
 391 park. Even though the average field size of 2.4 ha was similar to Achterhoek (2.1 ha), it consisted of
 392 many small fields (median 0.9 ha) and some very large fields (maximum size of 83 ha). Natural enemies
 393 had a smaller action radius than the pollinators. Their relative density was high close to the edges and
 394 decreases with distance into the field. Consequently, large fields result in large areas with low relative
 395 densities, greatly reducing the added effect of the strips in these large fields.

396 Comparing the coverages showed that the relative increase in natural pest control with a 2.5% additional
 397 coverage was almost linear in the Achterhoek: every 2.5% extra coverage gave about the same extra
 398 natural pest control (Fig. 4b-d). In Bornholm the change from the baseline scenario to 2.5% coverage
 399 with linear landscape elements gave the highest relative increase. While in Órség national park the
 400 largest relative increase occurred when changing from 2.5% to 5.0% coverage of the agricultural area

401 with linear landscape elements. The different types of linear landscape elements showed similar trends
 402 across coverages: a higher coverage implied higher ES supply. Corresponding to the simulation of the
 403 potential pollination, implementing hedgerows or flower strips provided however a larger supply than
 404 grassy strips. In all three case study areas a coverage of 2.5% with hedgerows or flower strips provided
 405 approximately the same additional potential supply of natural pest control as a coverage of 5.0% with
 406 grassy strips.

407
 408 Fig. 4 (a) relative predator density (%) for the three study areas under the baseline scenario; and the
 409 difference in supply in comparison with the baseline scenario for (b) the Achterhoek, (c) Bornholm, and
 410 (d) Örség National Park for the different coverages and different type of linear landscape elements (%).
 411 The graph shows the average ES supply across the five iterations, for each scenario and study area.

412 **3.1.3. Global climate regulation**

413 Fig. 5a shows that carbon sequestration (ton carbon/km²/year), as indicator for global climate regulation,
 414 was highest in Örség national park, and considerable lower for Bornholm. This difference could be
 415 explained again by the current land uses of the region (Fig. 1). Large parts of Örség national park were
 416 covered by forests, with a high carbon sequestration potential, while Bornholm is mostly covered by
 417 agricultural fields that have a low or zero net carbon sequestration. Note that information on farming
 418 practices relevant to carbon sequestration, such as catch crops, winter-green fields and Conservation
 419 Agriculture, is not included in the analysis. Figure 5b-d shows that adding hedgerows to the landscape
 420 gave larger amount of additional carbon sequestration than flower or grassy strips. In Bornholm covering
 421 2.5% of the agricultural area with hedgerows resulted in a 20% additional carbon sequestration and
 422 covering up to 12.5% resulted in a 40% additional carbon sequestration in comparison with the baseline
 423 situation. In the Achterhoek covering 12.5% of the agricultural area with hedgerows led to an addition
 424 18% of carbon sequestration. In Örség national park 12.5% coverage of the agricultural area led to only
 425 2.5% additional carbon sequestration in comparison with the baseline situation. This small increase could
 426 result from the high mean carbon sequestration in the baseline scenario in combination with the
 427 relatively large area of Örség national park.

428

429 Fig. 5 (a) mean carbon sequestration (ton C/km²/year) for the three study areas under the baseline
 430 scenario; and the difference in supply in comparison with the baseline scenario for (b) the Achterhoek,
 431 (c) Bornholm, and (d) Örség National Park for the different coverages and different type of linear
 432 landscape elements (%). The graph shows the average ES supply across the five iterations, for each
 433 scenario and study area.

434 3.1.4. Food provision

435 The indicator of food provision decreased with an increase in the coverage of linear landscape elements
 436 in the three study areas (Fig. 6). The decrease of food provision was linear and much steeper in the
 437 Achterhoek than in the two other study areas. The variation in the food provision estimated across the
 438 five iterations of each share of landscape covered by linear elements was very small, showing that the
 439 location of these linear elements does not affect the change in food provision. It is important to note that
 440 feedback loops, and therefore the potential positive effects of linear elements on crop yields through
 441 changes in other environmental parameters, such as micro-climate, were not taken into account in this
 442 study.

443

444 Fig. 6 (a) food provision (expressed in million Euro) for the study areas under the baseline scenario and
 445 (b) the change in food provision (%) for the different coverages of linear landscape elements in the three
 446 study areas compared to the baseline situation. The graph shows the average ES provision across the
 447 five iterations, for each scenario and study area.

448 *3.1.5. Aesthetics*

449 To estimate the ES landscape aesthetics we calculated an index based on three landscape metrics: mean
 450 shape index (SDI), to express naturalness (i.e. the degree of human disturbance) and Shannon's
 451 diversity (SDI) and Patch density (PD) for landscape diversity. We did this for the different coverages of
 452 the agricultural land with linear landscape elements (Fig. 7). Figure 7 shows that under the baseline
 453 situation the degree of human disturbance, or naturalness, was approximately the same for the three
 454 study areas. Landscape aesthetics in the baseline situation was the highest in the Achterhoek, where the
 455 landscape was already diverse and fragmented. While the MSI decreased in the three study areas,
 456 meaning that the shapes of the landscape elements were increasingly more regular, adding landscape
 457 elements to the landscape increased the values of the Shannon's diversity and of patch density. This
 458 means that all three regions the landscape became more diverse and fragmented by adding landscape
 459 elements.

460

461 Fig. 7 (a) aesthetics index for the study areas under the baseline scenario and (b) change in the
 462 aesthetics index based on three landscape metrics (mean shape index, Shannon's diversity and
 463 Patch density) to estimate landscape for the different coverages and different type of linear landscape
 464 elements. The graph shows the average ES supply across the five iterations, for each scenario and study
 465 area.

466 *3.1.6. Habitat maintenance*

467 Habitat maintenance increased with an increase in the area covered by linear elements, for the three
 468 study areas (Fig. 8). The share of (semi-)natural habitats increased with an increase in the area covered
 469 by linear elements. This increase depends however of the study area. Whereas the increase was strong
 470 in the Achterhoek and in Bornholm, it was much lower in the Órség National Park. The Shannon diversity
 471 index showing the diversity of land covers in the three study areas, was the highest in the Achterhoek,
 472 and the lowest in the Órség National Park. Achterhoek became more divers with implementing linear
 473 landscape elements, but the change was larger in Bornholm. Órség National Park became less divers, as
 474 the presence of (semi-)natural was already very high. Similar patterns could be found with respect to the
 475 distance to semi-natural elements. Initially the distance was the smallest in Órség National Park, and
 476 largest in Bornholm; in all study regions the distance decreased, when the share of linear elements
 477 increased. As for the other ESs, all the above mentioned trends were homogenous across the iterations
 478 of each share of landscape covered by linear elements, showing that the location of these linear elements
 479 doesn't affect the change in the habitat maintenance.

480
 481
 482

483

484 Fig. 8 (a) biodiversity index for the study areas under the baseline scenario and (b) Change in the
 485 biodiversity index based on three landscape metrics (landscape composition, Shannon's diversity and
 486 distance to (semi-)natural habitats) to estimate habitat maintenance for the different coverages and
 487 different type of linear landscape elements. The graph shows the average ES supply across the five
 488 iterations.

489 3.2. Trade-off analyses

490 Figure 9 shows the trade-offs between the six ESs indicators. While all regulating and cultural ESs
 491 increase under the scenarios with a 12.5% coverage of linear elements, the provisioning ES decreased in
 492 the three case study areas. Hedgerows seemed to be the type of linear elements that minimizes the
 493 trade-offs between provisioning and the other types of ESs as it led to the same reduction of food
 494 provision as the other types, while maximizing the increase of pollination, natural pest control, carbon
 495 sequestration, aesthetics and habitat maintenance.

496 The regulating and cultural ESs showed similar trends across the three study areas, all increasing overall
 497 with the implementation of linear elements, mainly with the increase in the woody linear elements. The
 498 changes induced by the adoption of the measures were overall higher for pest control in the Achterhoek,
 499 habitat maintenance in the Órség National Park and for all other ESs in Bornholm.

500

501

502 Fig. 9 Trade-offs and synergies between the six ESs for the baseline situation and the 12.5% coverage
 503 and different type of linear landscape elements in (a) the Achterhoek, (b) Bornholm and (c) Órség
 504 National Park.

505

506 4. Discussion and conclusion

507 In this study, we relied on existing and reproducible modelling approaches and a rich multi-source
 508 dataset to assess the changes in the supply of six indicators of ESs under several management scenarios
 509 in three multifunctional agricultural landscapes. We also analyzed trade-offs and bundles under these
 510 scenarios, at the landscape level. Our results highlight that the implementation of linear landscape
 511 elements can support high supply of multiple regulating and cultural ESs and give insights on the
 512 potential effectiveness of AECMs to achieve multiple environmental targets.

513 Our study goes beyond the assessment of the effects of AECM contracts or measures on a single
 514 environmental parameter, usually related to biodiversity conservation (Kleijn *et al.*, 2006; Blomqvist *et al.*,
 515 2009; Grondard *et al.*, under review). Our study contributes to the scientific literature demonstrating
 516 the overall positive effects of linear elements and more generally on agri-environmental practices that
 517 can stem from a set of AECM on multiple environmental parameters (Van Vooren *et al.*, 2017; Albrecht
 518 *et al.*, 2020). To do so, we followed a scenario modelling procedure, that proved to be of particular
 519 relevance, because the parameters of concern are complex to measure in the field (Sang, 2020). In
 520 addition, scenario analyses allowed us to estimate the potential impacts of policy measures in order to
 521 advice decision making processes, with a particular focus on the landscape context and trade-offs and
 522 synergies.

523 4.1. Overall positive, yet still contrasted, effects of linear elements on multiple ESs

524 Our results demonstrate the overall positive effects of linear elements on several ESs. Similarly to
 525 (Verhagen *et al.*, 2018) and (Albrecht *et al.*, 2020), we found that all measures could improve several
 526 environmental objectives simultaneously, although these objectives might depend on the practices (type
 527 of linear elements). We showed that the effects of the linear elements on ESs supply depended on the
 528 ESs. Whereas regulating and cultural ESs responded in a similar way to the implantation of linear

529 elements, the ES of food provision showed an opposite trend. The positive effects of any of the types of
530 linear elements on regulating and cultural ESs gradually increased with the increase in the amount of
531 linear elements across the landscape. The increase of linear elements implied a gradual decrease in the
532 agricultural used area leading to a decrease in the provisioning ES. This result is aligned with other
533 studies that highlighted the trade-offs between food production and regulating and cultural ESs in
534 agricultural landscapes (Ruijs *et al.*, 2013; Verhagen *et al.*, 2018) and an overall increase in ES supply
535 with an increased landscape heterogeneity (Botzas-Coluni *et al.*, 2021). While our results cannot give
536 evidence on how to minimize this trade-off by implementing AECMs based on linear landscape elements,
537 we showed that linear landscape elements can support a high level of multiple regulating and cultural
538 synergetic ES.

539 Our results also suggest that, while all types of linear elements had great potential in supplying multiple
540 ESs, their effect depended on the ESs, the types of linear elements and their amount in the landscape.
541 For instance, the increase in the potential pollination was most likely to occur with an increase of
542 hedgerows and in a lesser extend of flower strips, rather than with an increase of grassy strips. However,
543 we demonstrated that ESs responded differently to the type of linear elements. For example, when
544 flowers strips showed limited effects on the provision of C sequestration, they contributed to high level of
545 natural pest control.

546 We found that the consideration of the geographical contexts is critical when assessing the effects of
547 measures on multiple ESs. The effects of the linear elements on the supply of the six ESs were highly
548 context-dependent, i.e. depended on the biophysical and socio-economic characteristics of the landscape
549 and its environmental condition under the baseline scenario. Our results show that differences in the
550 effects of implementing landscape elements existed across our three study regions. When the supply of
551 the ESs was already high in the baseline situation, e.g., pollination in the Achterhoek, the changes
552 induced by the implementation of the linear elements were much lower than where the baseline situation
553 showed a lower initial supply of one or several of the ESs, e.g., pollination in Bornholm. The location of
554 those elements within the landscape did not affect the ESs, as reflected in the absence of variability of
555 the supply of the multiple ESs across the five iterations of each scenario. However, it is important to note
556 that our study did not account for the demand for these ESs. Yet, demand might vary across space,
557 leading to an increased effects of the linear elements in some places and lower effects in others.

558 4.2. Limitations of the study

559 Despite its strengths, our study shows three main limitations. First we only considered a limited set of six
560 ESs. Yet, agricultural areas provide a wider range of ES, such as water quality regulation and erosion
561 prevention (Zhang *et al.*, 2007; Galler *et al.*, 2015). However, we carefully chose the ESs indicators
562 based on scientific literature, data availability and expert knowledge. Our chosen indicators have two
563 major strengths. Firstly, they are diverse in terms of ES categories, as they cover regulating,
564 provisioning and cultural services, although the provisioning services are under-represented in
565 comparison to the other categories. Secondly, they allow a certain replicability of the method to other
566 agricultural landscapes.

567 Second, data availability and accuracy are crucial limitations when quantifying effects of interventions on
568 multiple ESs. For some areas, we were, for example, not able to link spatial data to actual agricultural
569 yield and price data. The level of detail of the data also varied from one study area to another. For
570 instance, the land use and land cover classification for the Dutch case study was much more detailed
571 than the classifications of the two other study areas. The supply of ESs other than the ones studied here,
572 such as soil related ES, rely on more complex ecological functions and might require more (detailed)
573 data. Modelling such ES across several local areas might be challenging due to the lack of accurate
574 available data. In addition, our land use land cover maps didn't account for the intensity levels within the
575 agricultural land use land cover classes. Yet, previous studies showed that intensity levels affect the
576 supply of multiple ESs in agricultural landscape (Le Clec'h *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, we didn't account
577 for the diversity of farming systems, e.g. conventional VS. organic that affect the supply of ESs, nor
578 consider some practical management considerations that would affect the farmers' practices, such as the
579 potential reduced accessibility for tractors.

580 Third, we modelled the six ESs in an independent way, without considering the feedback loops that might
581 occur when enhancing the supply of one ES. For instance, we did not consider the positive effects of
582 increased natural pest control on the use of pesticides which can have beneficial effects on pollinators.
583 We also did not consider the effect of enhanced pollination on crop yields, mainly because of limited
584 available data. In addition, we also did not consider the possible negative effects of linear elements on
585 crop yields due to, for example, spreading of weeds and rodents in the cropping area (Uyttenbroeck *et*
586 *al.*, 2016), nor the effect of shadows created by the hedgerows.

587 4.3. Management and policy implications

588 The results from our analysis have four main implications for land managers and policies addressing
589 agricultural management in European agriculture. First, our study demonstrates the potential of linear
590 elements to enhance pollination, natural pest control, C sequestration, landscape aesthetics and habitat
591 maintenance, across three study areas and types of linear elements. The enhancement of these ESs
592 increases with the amount of land covered by the linear landscape elements. This result suggests the
593 relevance of the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 (European and Directorate-General for, 2021)
594 published by the EU in 2021. This strategy commits to ensure that at least 10% of agricultural area is
595 under high-biodiversity landscape features such as buffer strips, hedgerows, ponds and non-productive
596 trees. In the Netherlands, the "Aanvalsplan landschapselementen"⁴ published at the invitation of the
597 Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality, ambitions to also include 10% landscape
598 elements in in the other parts of the cultural landscape (e.g. land without an agricultural function
599 belonging to municipalities and water boards).

600 Second, the diversity and the level of ESs provided by linear landscape elements imply that these linear
601 elements can help reducing several environmental pressures. Yet, these pressures might vary from one
602 area to another and the potential of linear elements to tackle them might vary from one type of linear
603 elements to another. The type of linear elements suggested in AECMs should them be thought carefully,
604 in regards of the most pressing challenges to be tackled in the targeted landscape. All types of linear
605 elements can support the maintenance of landscape diversity or enhance it, especially in places where
606 the aggregation of small parcels creates landscape homogenization and favor the landscape
607 intensification. By contributing to the landscape diversity, linear elements may support high level of
608 biodiversity and create opportunities for tourism, as desired in the Dutch and Hungarian case studies.
609 Unmown grassy strips can provide an important habitat for species in intensive landscape and can
610 contribute to mitigate the effects of agricultural intensification, that threatens the Hungarian case study.
611 Hedgerows may be suitable habitats for a number of endangered species (e.g., moths, warblers; Merckx
612 *et al.* (2010)) that are being threatened by the disappearance of shrubby habitats due to grassland
613 reconstructions by farmers (Hungarian case study). Hedgerows store more carbon than the croplands
614 and grasslands and therefore contribute to climate regulation (Drexler *et al.*, 2021), making then an
615 important element of climate neutral agricultural which is one of the ambition of the Island of Bornholm.
616 Future research could focus on understanding farmers' preferences and practical consideration
617 underpinning the decision making process to provide certain ESs to increase the adoption of AECMs and
618 its fit in the broader context of the landscape in which the AECMs are implemented. In addition, further
619 research should be conducted to bridge the gap between skewed distribution of the benefits for farmers
620 and the society at large versus the costs by the farmers induced by the adoption of environmentally
621 friendly practices, especially for ESs that currently have no markets.

622 Third, aligned with the results from Tschardt *et al.* (2005) and Krimmer *et al.* (2019) our results show
623 that linear elements are more effective in terms of ES supply in structurally simple landscapes (1–20%
624 semi-natural habitat) than in complex landscapes, such as the Órség National Park where the proportion
625 of (semi-)natural habitat is already high. Consequently, the EU target of 10% agricultural area under
626 high-biodiversity landscape features is likely to be more efficient in region such as Bornholm and the
627 Achterhoek than in Órség National Park. With this in mind, policy effectiveness of AECMs could be

⁴ <https://www.samenvoorbiodiversiteit.nl/updates/2021/03-maart/raamwerk-aanvalsplan-landschapselementen-deltaplan-biodiversiteitsherstel.pdf>

628 improved by targeting locations where the environmental benefits are expected to be higher than
629 average. Contrasted effectiveness of policy measures due to contrasted environmental conditions also
630 further rise the question of fair compensation to farmers that has been debated in the scientific literature
631 on Payments for Environmental Services (Karsenty *et al.*, 2017). Rewarding based on the efficiency of
632 the agri-environmental practices would neglect farmers who have already adopted nature-friendly
633 practices (Proctor *et al.*, 2008). Rewarding good practices rather than economic efficiency may, however,
634 encourage present and environmentally friendly behavior and its longevity (Muradian, 2013; Karsenty *et*
635 *al.*, 2017).

636 Four, the absence of variability of the supply of the multiple ESs at the landscape level across the five
637 iterations of each scenario suggests that spatial targeting of the AECMs is not critical, at least for linear
638 landscape elements in landscapes with homogenous and relatively flat topography. This might have
639 implications with respect to the choice between action- and result- oriented schemes, as the expected
640 supply of ESs is likely to be similar across one landscape and the risk of having lower ESs supply due to
641 geographical differences in that landscape being minimal. However, it is important to note that our case
642 study areas had relatively homogeneous topography, which might affected the variability of our findings.
643 Moreover, our models rely on simplification that some landscape characteristics were not considered in
644 our analyses, e.g. wind direction, aspect. Including these characteristics might affect the variability of
645 our findings.

646 Transferring our approach to larger areas, other agricultural landscapes and/or and more ESs could
647 reconcile institutional as well as practical requirements e.g., when designing agri-environmental policies.
648 This will allow to provide ex-ante information about incentive mechanisms supporting multiple ESs, ready
649 to cope with the challenges for agriculture in the future. To ensure the positive impact of our findings, as
650 being part of an ex-ante analysis, it would be of high importance to test them our findings with
651 stakeholders that have local knowledge and field experience before designing management plans.

652

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801 Appendix 1

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808 Figure A1 Spatial distribution of potential crop pollination in the three study areas: a-b) Achterhoek (the
809 Netherlands), c-d) Bornholm (Denmark) and e-f) Órség National Park (Hungary), for the baseline (a, c,

810 e) and for the situation where 12.5% of the whole utilized agricultural area was covered by hedgerows
811 (b, d, f).

815 Figure A2 Spatial distribution of relative predator density in crop fields in the three study areas: a-b)
816 Achterhoek (the Netherlands), c-d) Bornholm (Denmark) and e-f) Órség National Park (Hungary), for the
817 baseline (a, c, e) and for the situation where 12.5% of the whole utilized agricultural area was covered
818 by hedgerows (b, d, f).

Effects of linear landscape elements on ecosystem services supply and trade-offs in agricultural landscapes

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